

The Influence of the Concentration of Coagulating Electrolyte, Time and Temperature on the Syneresis of some Inorganic Jellies.

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In previous communications (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 152, 399; 1927, 164, 63; 1927, 166, 209) from these laboratories, it has been mentioned that stable jellies of ceric hydroxide, vanadium pentoxide and silicic acid undergo syneresis in course of time due to the decrease in the hydration tendency of the particles forming the jelly. The syneresis in a blood clot (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 459) has also been considered as a parallel case. Holmes, Kaufmann and Nicholas (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 1829), Mukoyama (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 42, 79), Fischer (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1922, 15, 3), Liepatov (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 41, 200), Kunitz (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1928, 12, 289), Kuhn (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 46, 299), Arsem (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 306), and Hardy (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1926, 112, 47) are the other investigators who have studied the phenomenon of syneresis in the case of silicic acid, viscose, soap jellies, dyestuffs, gelatine and other organic jellies. Very little work seems to have been done on the syneresis of inorganic jellies. In the present communication, we have studied the influences of the concentration of the coagulating electrolytes, of time, and of temperature on the syneresis of the following jellies:

Ponceaux red, ferric phosphate, ferric arsenate, chromium arsenate, vanadium pentoxide, zirconium hydroxide, zirconium borate, ferric borate and manganese dioxide.

A. Influence of Concentration of Coagulating Electrolytes and Time on Syneresis.

A known amount of the jelly-forming substance was taken in 50 c.c. Jena-glass conical flasks, and to it varying amounts of electrolytes of concentrations suitable for the formation of the jellies were added. The same total volume was made up by the addition of the requisite amount of water. The conical flasks were well corked and then sealed with wax in order to prevent the evaporation of water. The jellies were allowed to stand for a day or so and then the synerised

liquid was carefully poured in a measuring tube graduated to one-tenth of a cubic centimeter. The volume could be read up to 0.05 c.c. The readings were reproducible and quite comparative, and consequently the amount of syneresis was determined. In order to find out the influence of time, a similar set of jellies was allowed to stand for 90 minutes, and the syneresis during this period was compared with that obtained when allowed to stand for a day or so.

Ponceaux Red Jelly.

Varying amounts of *N*/10-barium chloride solution were added to 10 c.c. of 2.5% Ponceaux red. The total volume was made up to 20 c.c. in each case. The jellies were allowed to stand for 46 hours and the synerised liquid was then carefully measured.

TABLE I.

2.5% Ponceaux red solution taken = 10 c.c.

<i>N</i> /10. BaCl ₂ .	Total volume.	Synerised liquid in c.c.		Percentage of syneresis.		Syneresis in 46 hrs.
		90 mins.	46 hrs.	90 mins.	46 hrs.	BaCl ₂ .
8.5 c.c.	20 c.c.	—	0.95	—	4.75	0.112
9.0	20	0.1	1.20	0.5	6.00	0.133
9.5	20	0.2	1.50	1.0	7.50	0.158
10.0	20	0.45	2.80	2.25	11.5	0.230
11.0	21	—	2.60	—	12.4	0.236

It will be seen that the percentage of syneresis as well as the ratio between the amounts of syneresis and of coagulating electrolyte are increasing with the increase in the concentration of the electrolyte.

Ferric Phosphate Jelly.

The sol of ferric phosphate was prepared by adding potassium phosphate to ferric chloride solution in slight excess and dialysing the mixture for 11 days. The sol contained 54.74 g. of ferric phosphate per litre. To 10 c.c. of the sol taken in Jena flasks varying in amounts of *N*/5-potassium sulphate solution were added. The

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jellies were allowed to stand for 22 hours, and the amount of synerised liquid was measured.

TABLE II.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 20 c.c.

N/5- K ₂ SO ₄ .	Synerised liquid in c.c.		Percentage of syneresis.		Syneresis in 22 hrs.
	90 mins.	22 hrs.	90 mins.	22 hrs.	K ₂ SO ₄ .
2.0 c.c.	—	0	—	0	0
3.0	0.65	1.05	3.25	5.25	0.35
4.0	1.05	1.55	5.25	7.75	0.39
5.0	2.0	2.20	10.0	11.1	0.44
10.0	Precipitated.				

The percentage of syneresis and the ratio between the amount of syneresis and the concentration of the electrolyte increase as the concentration of the electrolyte increases.

Ferric Arsenate Jelly.

The sol of ferric arsenate was obtained by adding potassium arsenate solution to a ferric chloride solution till the precipitate formed just dissolved on shaking. The mixture was dialysed for 7 days. It contained 31.72 g. of ferric arsenate per litre. 10 C.c. of the sol were mixed with different amounts of normal potassium sulphate. The jellies were allowed to stand for 24 hours.

TABLE III.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 12 c.c.

N-K ₂ SO ₄ .	Synerised liquid in c.c.		Percentage of syneresis.		Syneresis in 24 hrs.
	90 mins.	24 hrs.	90 mins.	24 hrs.	K ₂ SO ₄ .
0.2 c.c.	—	0	—	0	0
0.3	0.2	1.15	1.67	9.58	3.83
0.4	1.1	1.50	9.17	12.50	3.75
0.5	1.4	1.70	11.67	14.17	3.40
0.7	—	1.95	—	16.25	2.80

The percentage amount of syneresis increases with the increase in the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte, whilst the ratio between the amount of syneresis and the electrolyte approaches a maximum and then decreases with the increase in the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte.

Chromium Arsenate Jelly.

The sol was obtained by adding potassium arsenate to chromic chloride solution in slight excess and dialysing the mixture for 5 days. The concentration of the sol was 57.6 g. chromium arsenate per litre. To 10 c.c. of the sol were added different amounts of normal potassium sulphate and the total volume was made up to 12 c.c. in every case. The jellies were allowed to stand for 24 hours before the syneresis was measured.

TABLE IV.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 12 c.c.

N-K ₂ SO ₄ .	Synerised liquid in c.c.		Percentage of syneresis.		Syneresis in 24 hrs.
	90 mins.	24 hrs.	90 mins.	24 hrs.	
0.2 c.c.	—	0	—	0	0
0.3	—	0.2	—	1.66	0.66
0.4	—	0.4	—	3.33	1.00
0.5	0.10	0.5	0.82	4.17	1.00
0.7	0.25	0.5	2.08	4.17	0.71
0.9	0.25	0.5	2.08	4.17	0.71
1.0	—	0.5	—	4.17	0.50

The amount of syneresis appears to increase with the increase in the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte. The ratio between the amount of syneresis and the electrolyte reaches a maximum and then decreases.

Vanadium Pentoxide Jelly.

Vanadic acid was precipitated by the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid to ammonium vanadate, and it was suspended in

water and dialysed for 5 days. The sol contained 4.62 g. of V_2O_5 per litre. To 10 c.c. of the sol, were added varying amounts of normal potassium chloride, and the jellies were allowed to stand for 22 hours before the amount of syneresis was measured.

TABLE V.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 12 c.c.

N-KCl.	Synerised liquid in c.c.		Percentage of syneresis.		Syneresis.
	90 mins.	22 hrs.	90 mins.	22 hrs.	in 22 hrs.
0.3 c.c.	—	0.45	—	3.75	1.50
0.5	—	0.70	—	5.83	1.40
0.7	0.4	0.95	3.33	7.91	1.85
0.9	0.5	1.10	4.17	9.17	1.20
1.1	1.7	1.30	5.83	10.83	1.18

The amount of syneresis increases and the ratio between the amount of syneresis and the concentration of the electrolyte decreases with the increase in the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte.

Zirconium Hydroxide Jelly.

The sol was prepared by dialysing a 10 per cent. solution of zirconium nitrate for 7 days. The concentration of the sol was 37.42 g. of ZrO_2 per litre. To 10 c.c. of the sol were added varying amounts of *N/5*-potassium sulphate and the jellies were allowed to stand for 26 hours before the syneresis was measured.

TABLE VI.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 15 c.c.

N/5-K ₂ SO ₄ .	Synerised liquid in c.c.		Percentage of syneresis.		Syneresis in 26 hrs.
	90 mins.	26 hrs.	90 mins.	26 hrs.	K ₂ SO ₄
3.5 c.c.	Not set	0	Not set	0	0
4.0	0	0.6	0	4.0	0.15
4.5	0.05	0.9	0.33	6.0	0.20

The percentage of syneresis and the ratio between the amount of syneresis and the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte increase with the concentration of the electrolyte.

Zirconium Molybdate Jelly.

The sol was prepared by dialysing a mixture of potassium molybdate and zirconium nitrate in excess for 4 days. The concentration of the sol was 45.2 g. of zirconium molybdate per litre. To 10 c.c. of the sol were added varying amounts of *N/5*-potassium sulphate and the jellies were allowed to stand for 24 hours before the synerised liquid was measured.

TABLE VII.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 12 c.c.

<i>N/5-K₂SO₄</i>	Synerised liquid in c.c.		Percentage of syneresis.		Syneresis in 24 hrs.
	90 mins.	24 hrs.	90 mins.	24 hrs.	<u>K₂SO₄</u>
0.5 c.c.	—	0	—	0	0
0.8	—	0	—	0	0
1.0	0	0.1	0	0.83	0.10
1.5	0.2	1.2	1.66	10.0	0.80
2.0	0.9	2.0	7.5	16.6	1.00

The percentage of the syneresis, as well as the ratio between the syneresis and the coagulating electrolyte increase as the concentration of the electrolyte increases.

Zirconium Borate Jelly.

The jelly was prepared by dialysing a mixture of zirconium nitrate and borax solutions. The concentration of the sol was 14.84 g. of zirconium borate per litre. It was dialysed for 8 days. To 10 c.c. of the sol were added varying amounts of *N/5*-potassium sulphate solution, and the jellies were allowed to stand for 24 hours before the syneresis was measured.

TABLE VIII.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 11.8 c.c.

N/5-K ₂ SO ₄ .	Synerised liquid in c.c.	Percentage of syneresis.	Syneresis
			K ₂ SO ₄ .
1.2 c.c.	1.7	14.4	1.41
1.4	2.5	21.2	1.78
1.6	2.85	24.1	1.78
1.8	3.20	27.1	1.77

It will be seen from the table that the syneresis increases with the increase in the concentration of the electrolyte, whereas the ratio between the two attains a maximum value and then decreases. The influence of time on syneresis is shown in the following table.

TABLE IX.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 11.2 c.c.

N/5-K ₂ SO ₄ .	Syneresis after 90 mins.	Syneresis after 24 hrs.
0.8 c.c.	0 c.c. = 0%	0.3 c.c. = 2.68%
1.0	0 = 0	1.3 = 11.6
1.2	0.4 = 3.57	2.0 = 17.8

Ferric Borate Jelly.

A sol was obtained by dialysing a mixture of borax and ferric chloride solution in excess for 90 days. The concentration of the sol was 82.48 g. of ferric borate per litre. To 10 c.c. of the sol were added varying amounts of normal potassium chloride and the jellies were allowed to stand for 24 hours before the synerised liquid was measured.

TABLE X.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume = 10.6 c.c.

N-KCl.	Synerised liquid in c.c.		Percentage of syneresis		Syneresis in 24 hrs.
	90 mins.	24 hrs.	90 mins.	24 hrs.	K ₂ SO ₄ .
0.2 c.c.	—	0.15	—	1.41	0.75
0.3	—	0.40	—	3.78	1.33
0.4	0.2	0.70	1.9	6.60	1.75
0.5	0.3	0.75	2.89	7.09	1.50
0.6	0.35	0.80	3.3	7.55	1.36

The amount of syneresis increases as the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte increases but the ratio between the amount of syneresis and the electrolyte approaches a maximum and then decreases.

Manganese Dioxide Jelly.

A 25 per cent. solution of glucose and a 10 per cent. caustic soda solution (2.566N) were prepared. To 2 c.c. of the glucose solution, 1 c.c. of caustic soda was added and varying amounts of 14 per cent. potassium permanganate solution (1.66N) were gradually added with constant stirring, and the mixture was all along cooled in ice. When the jelly was formed, it was allowed to stand for 90 minutes and then the synerised liquid was measured.

TABLE XI.

Caustic soda solution (2.566N) added each time = 1 c.c.
Total volume = 20 c.c.

25% Glucose.	14% KMnO ₄ .	Synerised liquid in c.c.		Percentage of syneresis.		Syneresis in 90 min.
		90 mins.	2 days.	90 mins.	2 days	KMnO ₄ .
2 c.c.	14 c.c.	1.1	—	5.5	—	0.078
2	15	1.3	3.7	6.5	18.5	0.087
1	16	1.85	4.4	9.25	23.0	0.116
2	17	2.3	4.8	14.0	24.0	0.165
3	18	0.9	—	4.5	—	0.056

The amount of syneresis increases as the amount of potassium permanganate increases and the ratio between the amount of syneresis and permanganate also increases. The addition of more glucose decreases the amount of syneresis.

B. *The Influence of Temperature on Syneresis.*

A known amount of sol was taken in 50 c.c. Jena flasks and mixed with different amounts of electrolytes and the volume was kept constant in every case. The flasks were well corked and allowed to stand in thermostats maintained at constant temperatures. Three sets of every jelly were prepared and one of them was allowed to

stand at the temperature of 80° and the other two at temperatures of 50° and 70° respectively. The jellies were kept at these temperatures for 90 minutes in every case. After this the synerised liquid was poured in a graduated measuring tube, and the amount of syneresis at different temperatures was thus measured.

The results obtained are recorded in the following tables. The values given in the column of temperature coefficients denote the increase in the amount of syneresis per 10° rise in temperature.

Ponceaux Red Jelly.

2.5 per cent. solution of the dyestuff taken each time=10 c.c.
 Total volume=20 c.c. Time given=90 minutes.

TABLE XII.

N/10- BaCl ₂ .	Amount of syneresis at			Temperature coefficients between	
	30°	50°	70°	30° and 50°	50° and 70°.
9.0 c.c.	0.1	0.1	0.2	0	0.05
9.5	0.2	0.45	0.7	0.125	0.125
10.0	0.45	0.6	0.8	0.075	0.100

Ferric Phosphate Jelly.

The sol was dialysed for 11 days. Concentration=54.74 g. ferric phosphate per litre.

Sol taken each time = 10 c.c. Total volume=20 c.c. Time given=90 minutes.

TABLE XIII.

N/5-K ₂ SO ₄ .	Amount of syneresis at			Temperature coefficients between	
	30°	50°	70°	30° and 50°	50° and 70°.
8 c.c.	0.65 c.c.	0.7 c.c.	1.15 c.c.	0.025	0.225
4	1.05	1.1	1.6	0.025	0.250
5	1.7	1.7	2.1	0.0	0.200

Ferric Arsenate Jelly.

The sol was dialysed for 7 days. Concentration=31.72 g. ferric arsenate per litre.

Sol taken each time=10 c.c. Total volume=12 c.c. Time given=90 minutes.

TABLE XIV.

N-K ₂ SO ₄ :	Amount of syneresis at			Temperature coefficient between	
	30°	50°	70°	30° and 50°	50° and 70°.
0.3 c.c.	0.2 c.c.	0.6 c.c.	0.9 c.c.	0.20	0.15
0.5	1.1	1.2	1.35	0.05	0.075
0.7	1.4	1.5	1.8	0.05	0.150

Chromium Arsenate Jelly.

Dialysed for 5 days. Concentration of the sol=57.6 g. chromium arsenate per litre. Sol taken each time=10 c.c. Total volume=12 c.c. Time given =90 minutes.

TABLE XV.

N-K ₂ SO ₄ :	Amount of syneresis at			Temperature coefficient between	
	30°	50°	70°	30° and 50°	50° and 70°.
0.5 c.c.	0.1 c.c.	0.3 c.c.	0.35 cc.	0.1	0.025
0.7	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.05	0.05
0.9	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.05	0.05

Vanadium Pentoxide Jelly.

Dialysed for 5 days. Concentration of the sol=4.62 g. V₂O₅ per litre. Sol taken each time=10 c.c. Total volume=12 c.c. Time given =90 minutes.

TABLE XVI.

N-KCl.	Amount of syneresis at			Temperature coefficient between	
	30°	50°	70°	30° and 50°	50° and 70°.
0.7 c.c.	0.4 c.c.	0.4 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	0	0.05
0.9	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.05	0.05
1.1	0.7	0.75	0.85	0.025	0.05

Zirconium Hydroxide Jelly.

Dialysed for 7 days. Concentration of the sol=37.42 g. ZrO_2 per litre. Sol taken each time=10 c.c. Total volume=15 c.c. Time given =90 minutes.

TABLE XVII.

$N/5-K_2SO_4$.	Amount of syneresis at			Temperature coefficient between	
	30°	50°	70°	30° and 50°	50° and 70°.
3.5 c.c.	Not set	0.05 c.c.	0.6 c.c.	—	0.275
4.0	0 c.c.	0.1	0.7	0.05	0.300
4.5	0.05	0.5	1.6	0.225	0.55

Zirconium Molybdate Jelly.

Dialysed for 4 days. Concentration of the sol=45.2 g. zirconium molybdate per litre. Sol taken each time=10 c.c. Total volume=12 c.c. Time given=90 minutes.

TABLE XVIII.

$N/5-K_2SO_4$.	Amount of syneresis at			Temperature coefficient between	
	30°	50°	70°	30° and 50°	50° and 70°.
1.0 c.c.	0 c.c.	0.1 c.c.	0.6 c.c.	0.05	0.25
1.5	0.2	0.6	1.8	0.20	0.60
2.0	0.9	1.9	3.2	0.50	0.65

Ferric Borate Jelly.

Dialysed for 30 days. Concentration of the sol=32.48 g. ferric borate per litre. Sol taken each time=10 c.c. Total volume=10.6 c.c. Time given=90 minutes.

TABLE XIX.

N-KCl.	Amount of syneresis at			Temperature coefficient between	
	30°	50°	70°	30° and 50°	50° and 70°.
0.4 c.c.	0.20 c.c.	0.20 c.c.	0.30 c.c.	0	0.05
0.5	0.30	0.30	0.35	0	0.035
0.6	0.35	0.40	0.45	0.025	0.025

Zirconium Borate Jelly.

Dialysed for 8 days. Concentration of the sol=14.84 g. zirconium borate per litre. Sol taken each time=10 c.c. Total volume=11.2 c.c. Time given=90 minutes.

TABLE XX.

N/5-K ₂ SO ₄ .	Amount of syneresis at			Temperature coefficient between	
	30°	50°	70°	30° and 50°	30° and 70°.
0.8 c.c.	0 c.c.	0.1 c.c.	0.6 c.c.	0.05	0.25
1.0	0	0.45	1.7	0.325	0.525
1.2	0.4	1.4	2.4	0.500	0.500

Manganese Dioxide Jelly.

25 per cent. glucose solution taken each time=2 c.c.

2.566N-Caustic soda added=1 c.c. Total volume=20 c.c.

Strength of potassium permanganate solution=1.66N

The jellies have been formed at 0°, and then transferred to baths maintained at 15° and 30°, and they were allowed to stand for 90 minutes before the syneresis was measured.

TABLE XXI.

KMnO ₄ .	Amount of syneresis at		Temperature coefficient.
	15°	30°	
14 c.c.	1.1 c.c.	2.5 c.c.	0.93
15	1.3	2.8	4.00
16	1.85	2.9	0.7
17	2.8	3.2	0.27

The results recorded in the foregoing tables bring out the following facts:

Whenever a jelly is formed by the addition of coagulating electrolytes, (a) the amount of syneresis increases as the concentration of the electrolyte increases and (b) the ratio between the amount of syneresis and the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte either increases continually or tends to attain a maximum and then it diminishes with the concentration of the electrolyte. Thus the amount of syneresis does not increase in the same proportion as the coagulating electrolyte. The jellies of ferric arsenate, chromium arsenate, zirconium borate and ferric borate show the maximum clearly, whilst those of ponceaux red, ferric phosphate, zirconium hydroxide zirconium molybdate and manganese dioxide show the continuous increase in the ratio between the amount of syneresis and the concentration of the electrolyte as the concentration of the electrolyte increases.

Syneresis is likely to be due to a decrease in the hydration and it appears that on allowing some of the jellies to stand for some time, hydration tendency of the particles and the free surface become less and this causes the shrinkage of the network. It has been observed that the addition of an excess of electrolyte in coagulating the sol, accelerates the agglomeration of the particles and diminishes the hydration. Thus shortly after setting of the jelly, the excess of the electrolyte brings about the syneresis, and if the electrolyte is in large excess, the jelly will not set at all but a gelatinous precipitate will be obtained. Thus on increasing the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte, the following may happen (Prakash and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 408).

- (i) Up to a limit—no jelly formation;
- (ii) Up to the second limit—stable jellies undergoing no appreciable syneresis;
- (iii) Between the second and third limits—firm jellies readily synerising;
- (iv) Above the third limit—no jelly formation but a gelatinous precipitate is obtained.

Between the second and third limits, the phenomenon of syneresis is observed. In this limit, the increase in the concentration of the electrolyte always increases the amount of syneresis. The ratio between the amount of syneresis and the concentration

of the electrolyte sometimes increases continuously and sometimes attains a maximum as the concentration of the electrolyte is increased.

It has been observed that the syneresis starts a short time after the setting of the jelly, and the amount of syneresis increases as the time advances. After a certain time, the rate of the increase of syneresis diminishes and then syneresis stops. On allowing the jelly to stand further, no marked difference in the amount of syneresis will be observed. It has been seen that in the inorganic jellies investigated, this stage is attained in about two days. The increment in the percentage of the syneresis at two different intervals of time, sometimes diminishes with the concentration of the electrolyte (as in the case of ferric arsenate, chromium arsenate, and ferric borate jellies), sometimes increases (as in the cases of ponceaux red, zirconium hydroxide, zirconium molybdate and zirconium borate) and sometimes attains a maximum (as in the case of ferric phosphate, vanadium pentoxide and manganese dioxide) and as such no definite relationship between electrolyte-effect and time-effect has been observed. It appears that in most cases, the time-effect will either increase or attain a maximum with the increase in the concentration of the electrolyte.

The temperature-effect on the syneresis of many jellies has also been studied. It has been observed that the amount of syneresis is markedly increased at higher temperatures. Syneresis at three temperatures (30°, 50° and 70°) has been investigated, and it is found that the temperature coefficient between 30° and 50° is much less in all cases than between 50° and 70°.

Some of the jellies have almost no tendency towards syneresis. The jellies of thorium arsenate, phosphate and molybdate, and the jellies of iron, chromium and aluminium hydroxides do not undergo any syneresis even when kept for a long time. The syneresis has also been observed in the jellies of stannic hydroxide, borate and tungstate.

Arsem (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 306) advances the view that structural arrangement of units in a gel is inherently unstable, and he supposes that a further condensation of the associated phase is possible through three agencies: the re-orientation of units, the release of loosely combined molecules of the liquid phase and the union of previously non-functioning residual valencies. Wherever, there is a complete re-orientation of the structural units of a gel,

it reverts to a mixture of crystals and free liquid. According to him, the syneresis is due to the shrinkage of solid phase caused by progressive association and re-orientation of molecular units.

In a previous communication (*loc.cit.*), we have shown that the nature of a jelly is determined by two factors: the hydration tendency of the particles, and secondly the agglomeration tendency; and when the hydration tendency predominates over the agglomeration tendency, the jellies obtained are comparatively more transparent and stable and there is less possibility of the shrinkage of the network, and such jellies do not synerise to an appreciable extent. But whenever there is a diminution in hydration and increase in the agglomeration, the jellies are opaque and their stability is also diminished; and with more and more of the agglomeration, the possibility of the shrinkage of the jelly structure becomes greater, and then the jelly either partially gives up the liquid phase or is completely precipitated. The re-orientation of the molecular units to account for the syneresis in a jelly, does not appear to be essential and probable and the whole phenomenon of syneresis can be easily explained on the hydration and agglomeration hypothesis. Our results on the influence of the concentration of electrolytes on the amount of syneresis are in agreement with it. We have found that as the concentration of the electrolytes is increased, the amount of syneresis is also increased. The addition of coagulating electrolyte to a jelly-forming sol diminishes the charge on the colloidal particles, and the hydration is increased till a jelly is obtained, and by adding a further amount of electrolyte, the same forces which bring about the hydration, cause the particles to agglomerate, and the structure of the jelly undergoes a shrinkage. The increment in the temperature is also favourable for agglomeration and as such we have found that at higher temperatures, there is more syneresis in jellies.

Hardy (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, 112, 59) has studied the relation of syneresis to the freezing of the gel which he accounts on the basis of hydration and dehydration of the particles. He regards the swelling of gelatine as negative syneresis.

Most of the inorganic jellies investigated do not completely synerise even after the interval of several days; and had the re-orientation of the molecular units, as Arsem (*loc. cit.*) thinks, been the only cause of the syneresis, the amount of syneresis would have been continuously increased, as the ageing is increased, for, there

is no reason why re-orientation should stop after a time till it is not complete. From our results we have shown that the amount of the coagulating electrolyte added to a jelly controls the extent of syneresis. There is always a fixed minimum of the amount of the electrolyte necessary to give a permanent jelly, and any amount greater than that will cause syneresis. The greater the excess of the electrolyte over this fixed minimum, the greater will be the syneresis. The extent to which this syneresis will proceed will always depend upon the excessive electrolyte, and as such with a definite amount of electrolyte, the jelly is never completely synerised.

According to von Weimarn (*Rep. Imp. Ind. Res. Inst. Osaka*, 1928, 9, 1) the total amount of water imbibed in a jelly is supposed to consist of (i) interatomic hydration, e.g., water in crystal hydrates, (ii) 'surface hydration' and (iii) 'structure hydration' i.e., water enclosed by the pores of the structural elements of the jelly. No quantitative data appear to be available as regards the interatomic hydration of these jellies, of which even the crystalline nature is doubtful; and yet, if some liquid exists in this state, it does not influence much the nature of a jelly. Surface hydration is the prime factor in the process of gelation and we have emphasised that this originates from gradual and regular charge neutralisation of hydrophile colloids by suitable electrolytes present. When hydration has reached a maximum stage, jelly elements are formed. These elements then, owing to their residual forces which would have otherwise brought about the agglomeration, imbibe the whole of the remaining solvent and give a solid jelly.

The process of syneresis is accompanied by the squeezing out of the liquid and shrinkage of the solid mass. Even in those jellies, which synerise to a great extent like blood clot or vanadium pentoxide, the whole of the solvent is never squeezed out, and the solid mass remaining after the maximum syneresis is still gelatinous in nature. This goes to show that the particles are still hydrated. When a jelly has been formed, the excess of the coagulating electrolyte tends to bring about the agglomeration and dehydration of the particles. This agglomeration tendency is the cause of the shrinkage of the solid mass. When particles have been slightly dehydrated, the 'structurally' imbibed water becomes loosened and comes out as the synerised product. Thus the synerised liquid appears to be mostly the liquid caught in the network of the jelly and partly formed by the dehydration of the particles.

Some jellies break up completely but do not show ordinary syneresis. The case of the true syneresis should be distinguished from that of the breaking up of a jelly. In the case of truly synerised bodies, the mass remaining after the maximum syneresis is still much hydrated, but in the other case, the jelly leads to a justly dehydrated powder settling to the bottom. Most of the von Weimarn jellies, after a few hours (and some after a few days) leave, only the precipitated dehydrated mass and the separated solvent. This may be called the breaking up of a jelly, and not the true syneresis. Here the agglomeration and dehydration tendency is so great that the jellies are unstable and the solid precipitates out after a short time. Similar is the case with the manganese dioxide jelly prepared by Weitzemann's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 1082; 1917, 39, 27). An interesting case has been observed with thorium molybdate jellies. Most of these jellies are very stable and do not undergo any syneresis (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 590), but some of these jellies which have been prepared by the use of a large amount of potassium molybdate, precipitate out without undergoing any proper syneresis after ten or twelve days. This precipitation is due to the marked dehydration of the superficially hydrated jelly-elements and is brought about by the excess of the potassium molybdate present. Thus, in true syneresis, the jelly elements are never completely dehydrated, and it is mainly the structurally imbibed liquid which is squeezed out. In the case of precipitation or breaking up of the jelly, dehydration of the elements appears practically complete.

Usher (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, A125, 143) claims to have been successful in gelatinising such lyophobic substances as cadmium sulphide and gamboge in presence of suitable concentrations of sodium chloride. He assumes that whenever the solid framework of a rigid two-phase system becomes thickened in consequence of internal packing, the system becomes physically heterogeneous and hence undergoes syneresis. However, this explanation does not appear to be adequate in view of the fact that even dilute jellies where internal packing is not so dense, undergo marked syneresis, and some of the concentrated jellies also do not synerise.

Summary.

1. The influence of the concentration of coagulating electrolytes, time and temperature on the syneresis of the following jellies has been investigated:

Ponceaux red, ferric arsenate, ferric phosphate, ferric borate, chromium arsenate, vanadium pentoxide, zirconium hydroxide, zirconium molybdate, zirconium borate, and manganese dioxide.

2. It has been found that whenever a jelly is formed by the addition of electrolytes to a jelly-forming sol, the amount of syneresis increases continuously with the concentration of the electrolyte and the ratio between the amount of syneresis and the concentration of the electrolyte either increases or attains a maximum with the increase in the concentration of the electrolyte.

3. The amount of syneresis increases with time in the beginning but further syneresis stops after an interval. In the jellies investigated, the maximum syneresis is obtained within two days.

4. It has been observed that the amount of syneresis in the above jellies is greater at higher temperatures. The temperature coefficient of syneresis between 50° and 70° is invariably higher than that between 80° and 50° .

5. The phenomenon of syneresis has been explained on the hydration and agglomeration hypotheses of the jelly-forming particles. It has been advanced that the amount of coagulating electrolytes added to a jelly-forming sol controls not only the nature of the jelly, but also the extent of syneresis. There is always a fixed minimum of the amount of the coagulating electrolyte necessary to give a stable jelly, and any amount greater than that will bring about the syneresis. The addition of large amounts of electrolytes gives only a gelatinous precipitate, and not a jelly, because in that case, the agglomeration tendency of the particles predominates over the hydration tendency.

6. The true syneresis is quite distinct from that of the breaking up of a jelly. In true syneresis, the particles even after the maximum syneresis remain hydrated and gelatinous, while in the other case, a precipitated dehydrated mass is obtained. It is mainly the structurally imbibed liquid which is squeezed out during the true syneresis.

7. The idea that syneresis is due to the re-orientation of the particles appears to be inadequate, and similarly the view that this phenomenon is due to the heterogeneity produced by the intense internal packing of the particles also appears to be unsatisfactory.